

THE ROLE OF CRITICAL THINKING INTO CLL APPROACH

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Abstract:

This article investigates the integration of critical thinking abilities into communicative language learning (CLL). It contends that CLL, by emphasizing authentic communication and meaning-focused language use, provides a natural framework for cultivating critical thinking. In article are discussed many techniques for introducing critical thinking into CLL courses, including authentic assignments, critical thinking questions, group discussions, media analysis, and error analysis. By applying these tactics, teachers can enable students to not only improve their language abilities but also encourage critical analysis, evaluation, and synthesis.

Key words: communicative language learning, critical thinking, language teaching, language learning, critical inquiry, authentic tasks, group discussions, media analysis, error analysis.

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Introduction

In today's information-driven society, critical thinking has become an essential talent for anyone seeking to manage complicated challenges and make sound judgement. While traditional language learning has focused on grammar and vocabulary, a more holistic approach that incorporates critical thinking can help students not only speak effectively, but also critically assess, evaluate, and synthesize knowledge. This study investigates how communicative language learning (CLL) can be an effective strategy for developing critical thinking skills among language learners.

Communicative Language Learning and Critical Thinking:

CLL is an educational approach that focuses on the use of language for authentic communication. It emphasizes meaning above form, fostering a learning atmosphere that enables students to engage in real-world language usage. This strategy readily fits with the development of critical thinking skills by requiring students to:

- Analyze information: In order to participate effectively in communication exchanges, students must process and analyze message content².
- Evaluate arguments: They must examine the validity and trustworthiness of information offered to them, taking into account evidence, reasoning, and bias³

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² Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2001). *Approaches and methods in language teaching* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.

³ Skehan, P. (1996). *Second language acquisition research*. Oxford University Press.

- Synthesize ideas: Students must mix information from many sources to develop fresh insights and viewpoints.

CLL can also help students develop other valuable cognitive skills, such as problem-solving, creativity, and cultural awareness. CLL is often used in conjunction with other language teaching methods, such as task-based language teaching (TBLT) and content-based language teaching (CBLT).

CLL has been shown to be effective in improving students' language proficiency and communicative competence.

Strategies to Integrate Critical Thinking into CLL

Authentic Tasks:

Using authentic tasks that mimic real-world communication situations can significantly enhance critical thinking skills. These tasks provide students with opportunities to apply their language knowledge in meaningful contexts. For example, engaging in debates, role-playing exercises, or simulations can challenge students to assess information, formulate arguments, and respond to different perspectives.

Critical Thinking Questions:

Incorporating critical thinking questions into your lessons can encourage students to delve deeper into the subject matter. Instead of asking simple factual questions, pose questions that require analysis, evaluation, and synthesis. For instance, instead of asking "What is the capital of France?", inquire "Why is Paris considered a cultural center?" Such questions stimulate higher-order thinking and promote critical reflection.

Group Discussions:

Facilitating group discussions allows students to share their thoughts, question assumptions, and engage in respectful dialogue. These discussions can help students improve their listening skills, analyze opposing viewpoints, and develop well-reasoned arguments. By participating in collaborative activities, students learn to value diverse perspectives and engage in constructive communication.

Media Analysis:

Utilizing various media, such as news articles, videos, or advertisements, can be an effective tool for developing critical thinking skills. Students can analyze the content of these materials, identify biases, and evaluate the credibility of the source. This practice helps students become discerning consumers of information and develop the ability to critically assess media messages.

Error Analysis:

Encouraging students to analyze their own and their peers' language errors can lead to a deeper understanding of language rules and improve their ability to self-correct and make informed language choices. By examining errors, students can identify patterns, understand the underlying grammatical or lexical concepts, and apply this knowledge to their own language production.

Conclusion

Teachers can provide students with the necessary skills for success in today's complicated environment by including critical thinking into communicative language acquisition. Teachers may empower students to become not only proficient language learners, but also critical thinkers capable of making informed decisions

and contributing meaningfully to society, by creating a learning environment that stimulates critical inquiry, analysis, and review.

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